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Abstract:

Performance of a bank indicates the strength and weakness of that particular bank by properly establishing the association between the items of the balance sheet and profit and loss account. The researcher has undertaken the study of performance evaluation of Tamilnadu Grama Bank in Salem District, Tamilnadu State for the period from 2019-2020 to 2022-2023. The research is descriptive and analytical in nature. The data used for the study was secondary in nature. The data used for the study was to analyze the performance of the Tamilnadu Grama Bank on the basis of Trend Analysis. The study found that the bank is weak in position and has shown the declining trend in the initial period of the study period and later it has shown a positive trend.

Key Words: Performance Evaluation, Grama Bank

Introduction:

Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) which are hybrid institutions combining the role of co-operative with commercial banking functions have been the most intensively debated subject in recent years. Indian banking system today is evolving itself a powerful instrument of planning for economic growth. Among the various factors of economic development and consequent removal of poverty the role of financial institutions is very significant. The overall development of the economy depends to a large extent on the banking sector as financial institutions act as suppliers of capital for production of goods and services, which in turn raises income and standard of living of the people.

In India, the banking sector has received from time to time definite orientations, and this sector has come to occupy a predominant position among the infrastructural factors of economic development. In our country where 74.2 per cent of population lives in rural areas, banks are relied upon to play a key role in rural uplift. An efficient system of purveying institutional credit in rural and semi-urban areas is an essential ingredient of any viable strategy for the removal of poverty and modernization of our economy at base level.

India is a country of villages and development of the country depends upon all round progress of rural areas. That is why Mahatma Gandhi said in Harijan, "I have believed and repeated times without number that India is not found in its few cities but in its 7,00,000 villages. I would say that if the village perishes, India will perish too". So the development of rural sector has become one of the concerns of the country's Five Year Plans which can achieve their objects only by the fillip given to rural development activities.

The idea of 'Rural Bank' was first suggested by the Bengal National Chamber of Commerce in its memorandum to the Rural Banking Enquiry Committee, 1950. It suggested setting up of one rural bank in each taluk with a paid-up capital of Rs.1 lakh, with permission to scheduled banks to sponsor it in rural areas. The sponsor banks were expected to contribute 50 per cent of the capital of each rural bank and the balance by the public or the provincial Government. This was an interesting suggestion which contained the essence of modern Regional Rural Banks.

History of Tamilnadu Grama Bank (TGB):

The Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) were conceptualised by the Narsimham committee in 1975 to combine the local feel and familiarity of rural problems characteristic of cooperatives with the professionalism and large resource base of commercial banks. Subsequently, the RRBs were set up through the promulgation of RRB Act of 1976.

Pandyan Grama Bank:

Pandyan Grama Bank, under the sponsorship of Indian Overseas Bank came into existence on 09.03.1977 with its Head Office at Sattur, covering undivided Ramanathapuram and Tirunelveli districts.

Pallavan Grama Bank:

Adhiyaman Grama Bank, under the sponsorship of Indian Bank came into existence on 27.12.1985 covering Dharmapuri and Krishnagiri districts with its Head Office at Dharmapuri.

Vallalar Grama Bank, also under the sponsorship of Indian Bank, came into existence on 19.06.1986, and covered undivided South Arcot district (bifurcated into Cuddalore and Villupuram districts) with its Head Office at Cuddalore.

As per Central Government's directive of One State, One RRB per Sponsor bank concept both Vallalar Grama Bank and Adhiyaman Grama Banks were merged on 31.08.2006 to form Pallavan Grama Bank, headquartered at Salem.

Tamil Nadu Grama Bank:

Subsequently, as per Central Government's directive of "One State One RRB" concept both Pallavan Grama Bank and Pandyan Grama Bank were amalgamated into a new entity 'Tamil Nadu Grama Bank' with effect from 01.04.2019 having its Head Office at Salem under the sponsorship of Indian Bank.

Area of Operation:

Prior to amalgamation, Pallavan Grama Bank with its Headquarters at Salem functioned in 16 districts and Pandyan Grama Bank with its Headquarters at Virudhunagar functioned in 16 districts of Tamilnadu. After amalgamation, the Bank is operating in 37 Districts of Tamil Nadu except Chennai with its Headquarters at Salem.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objectives of the study are mentioned bellow:

- The main purpose of the study is to examine the performance of the bank in mobilizing deposits.
- To analyze the position of loan and advances issued by the bank.
- To identify the NPA position and working result of the bank.
- To find out ways and means for improving the efficiency and effectiveness in the operation of bank.

Period of Study:

The study covered four years from March 2020 to March 2023.

Data and Tools:

The study is mainly based on secondary data drawn from annual reports of the respective banks and other corporate databases. The data is related to four years (2020-2023). For the purpose of the study, the research instrument used for the Trend analysis of deposits, loans and advances and investments has been used. Apart from this, statistical tools such as mean (x), standard deviation (STDEV), Coefficient of Variation (C.V) and Trend Analysis are used.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Trend Analysis:

The financial data in absolute rupees for various years can also be expressed in percentages to indicate and analyze the trend in various years. Such a trend is called Trend analysis. With the help of the methods of least squares we can fit either straight line trend or a second-degree parabola. The equation of the straight line or linear trend is;

$$Y_c = a + bx$$

Where, Y_c represents the Variable, X represents the Time period, A and B are two Constants.

The value of A & B is obtained by solving the following two normal equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum Y &= Na + b\sum X \\ \sum XY &= a\sum X + b\sum X^2 \end{aligned}$$

1. Share Capital:

Share capital occupies an important position among the owned funds. Share capital is the very foundation of any business organization and in case of Tamilnadu Grama Bank which creates its own power to build up its borrowing capacity.

Table 1: Trend Values by the method of Least Squares for Share Capital

(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Share Capital	Trend Value	Fluctuation
March 2020	46.95	46.95	0.00
March 2021	46.95	46.95	0.00
March 2022	46.95	46.95	0.00
March 2023	46.95	46.95	0.00
Mean	46.95		
STDEV	0.00		
C.V	0.00		

(Source: Annual reports)

The above table shows an analysis of the trend value of share capital showed a no annual increase over a period of four years. The comparison of trend value with share capital showed a no fluctuating trend.

2. Reserve Fund:

The reserves are made out of net profits of the bank. It consists of Statutory Reserves and other reserves available for distribution of dividends to members. The position of reserve fund which indicates the health of the bank which is presented in below Table.

Table 2: Trend Values by the method of Least Squares for Reserve Fund

(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Reserve Fund	Trend Value	Fluctuation
March 2020	1185.62	1134.39	51.23
March 2021	1370.13	1406.94	-36.81
March 2022	1599.41	1679.49	-80.08
March 2023	2017.69	1952.04	65.65
Mean	1543.21		
STDEV	358.76		
C.V	23.25		

(Source: Annual reports)

The above table shows an analysis of the trend value of reserve fund showed an annual increase of Rs.1952.04 crore over a period of four years. The comparison of trend value with reserve fund showed a fluctuating trend. In these years March 2021 and March 2022, showed a negative fluctuation and in the remaining years it showed a positive fluctuation.

3. Deposits:

The bank accepts various kinds of deposits both from members and non-members such as current deposit, saving deposit, fixed deposit, recurring deposit and other deposit schemes.

Table 3: Trend Values by the method of Least Squares for Deposits

(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Deposits	Trend Value	Fluctuation
March 2020	12463.38	12389.53	73.85
March 2021	14858.82	14855.50	3.32
March 2022	17093.28	17321.48	-228.20
March 2023	19938.48	19787.45	151.03
Mean	16088.49		
STDEV	3187.76		
C.V	19.81		

(Source: Annual reports)

The above table shows an analysis of the trend value of deposits showed an annual increase of Rs.19787.45 crore over a period of four years. The comparison of trend value with deposits showed a fluctuating trend. In these years March 2022, showed a negative fluctuation and in the remaining years it showed a positive fluctuation.

4. Borrowings:

The TGBs are generally borrowed from RRB and other financing agencies. The maximum borrowing power of the TGB may be fixed at 25 times of the owned fund. To extend loans and advances to members and to maintain fluid resources and liquidity, the TGB should ask for the higher financing agencies from RRB for its financial accommodation.

Table 4: Trend Values by the method of Least Squares for Borrowings

(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Borrowings	Trend Value	Fluctuation
March 2020	4572.55	5183.47	-610.92
March 2021	6594.71	5991.25	603.46
March 2022	7424.87	6799.02	625.85
March 2023	6988.41	7606.80	-618.39
Mean	6395.14		
STDEV	1261.48		
C.V	19.73		

(Source: Annual reports)

The above table shows an analysis of the trend value of borrowings showed an annual increase of Rs.7606.80 crore over a period of four years. The comparison of trend value with borrowings showed a fluctuating trend. In these years March 2020 and March 2023, showed a negative fluctuation and in the remaining years it showed a positive fluctuation.

5. Investments:

The selected sample bank invests their surplus funds in trusted securities, and other financial agencies in the form of share capital and deposits.

Table 5: Trend Values by the method of Least Squares for Investments

(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Investments	Trend Value	Fluctuation
March 2020	2441.72	2351.64	90.08
March 2021	2596.86	2707.95	-111.09
March 2022	3016.18	3064.26	-48.08

March 2023	3489.65	3420.57	69.08
Mean	2886.10		
STDEV	469.87		
C.V	16.28		

(Source: Annual reports)

The above table shows an analysis of the trend value of investments showed an annual increase of Rs.3420.57 crore over a period of four years. The comparison of trend value with investments showed a fluctuating trend. In these years March 2021 and March 2022, showed a negative fluctuation and in the remaining years it showed a positive fluctuation.

6. Working Capital:

The demands of the members and customers, the bank has to maintain working capital. The management of current assets, current liabilities and inter-relationship between them is termed as working capital management.

Table 6: Trend Values by the method of Least Squares for Working Capital

(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Working Capital	Trend Value	Fluctuation
March 2020	12222.22	12599.29	-377.07
March 2021	15042.11	14264.24	777.87
March 2022	15504.66	15929.19	-424.53
March 2023	17617.88	17594.15	23.73
Mean	15096.72		
STDEV	2220.24		
C.V	14.71		

(Source: Annual reports)

The above table shows an analysis of the trend value of working capital showed an annual increase of Rs.17594.15 crore over a period of four years. The comparison of trend value with working capital showed a fluctuating trend. In these years March 2020 and March 2022, showed a negative fluctuation and in the remaining years it showed a positive fluctuation.

7. Loans and Advances:

The resources of the TGBs are invested in the form of loans and advances. The lending policy of a TGB is laid down in its bye-laws. However, it is also subjected to the directives of the RRB.

Table 7: Trend Values by the method of Least Squares for Loans and Advances

(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Loans and Advances	Trend Value	Fluctuation
March 2020	11749.18	11997.54	-248.36
March 2021	14469.14	13878.18	590.96
March 2022	15321.97	15758.83	-436.86
March 2023	17733.72	17639.47	94.25
Mean	14818.50		
STDEV	2469.46		
C.V	16.66		

(Source: Annual reports)

The above table shows an analysis of the trend value of loans and advances showed an annual increase of Rs.17639.47 crore over a period of four years. The comparison of trend value with loans and advances showed a fluctuating trend. In these years March 2020 and March 2022, showed a negative fluctuation and in the remaining years it showed a positive fluctuation.

8. Non-Performing Assets:

An Asset becomes 'Non-Performing' when it ceases to generate income for a bank. This happens when interest or installment principal or both are not received on due dates and the delay exceeds a 'Stipulated Time'.

Table 8: Trend Values by the method of Least Squares for Non-Performing Assets

(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Non -Performing Assets	Trend Value	Fluctuation
March 2020	22.17	24.32	-2.15
March 2021	22.93	19.08	3.85
March 2022	12.60	13.84	-1.24
March 2023	8.14	8.60	-0.46
Mean	16.46		
STDEV	7.27		
C.V	44.17		

(Source: Annual reports)

The above table shows an analysis of the trend value of Non-Performing Assets showed an annual increase of Rs.24.32 crore over a period of four years. The comparison of trend value with Non-Performing Assets showed a fluctuating trend. In these years March 2020, March 2022 and March 2023, showed a negative fluctuation and in the remaining year it showed a positive fluctuation.

9. Net Profit:

Profitability is an indication of the efficiency with which the operations of the banks are carried out. Poor operational efficiency results in poor profits. Members are interested to know the profitability of the banks as it indicates the return which they can get on their investments. Even though Tamilnadu Grama Bank is not profit-making institutions, some amount of profit is to be earned in order to augment their own sources to provide for statutory and other reserves and to pay a reasonable return on its share capital. Besides, profit also helps in boosting public confidence. So an evaluation of the profitability of the banks is dispensable which may indicate the overall efficiency of the banks.

Table 9: Trend Values by the method of Least Squares for Net Profit

(Rs. in Crore)

Year	Net Profit	Trend Value	Fluctuation
March 2020	149.62	117.81	31.81
March 2021	184.51	202.89	-18.38
March 2022	229.28	287.96	-58.68
March 2023	418.28	373.04	45.25
Mean	245.42		
STDEV	119.76		
C.V	48.80		

(Source: Annual reports)

The above table shows an analysis of the trend value of Net profit showed an annual increase of Rs.373.04 crore over a period of four years. The comparison of trend value with Net profit showed a fluctuating trend. In these years March 2021 and March 2022, showed a negative fluctuation and in the remaining years it showed a positive fluctuation.

Findings:

- The share capital position of the bank revealed a constant trend in the study period.
- The reserve fund of the bank revealed the increasing trend in the study period.
- The deposits of the bank registered much fluctuating trend.
- The borrowings position of the bank had heavily increased.
- The investments, working capital and loans and advances of the bank revealed the increasing trend in the study period.
- The provision allocated for the NPA of the bank depicted increasing trend.
- The net profit of the bank was found positive position and some fluctuation also found.

Suggestions:

- The bank should increase its share capital base for better financial position.
- The bank should take steps to trap more number of deposits from its members and public people.
- The working capital should be maintained sufficiently by the bank in order to meet the expenses.
- The bank has to increase reserved fund adequately for managing uncertainties.
- The bank must try to increase their lending activities which in turn increase its learning income.
- The bank should be keen to efficiently improve the position of net profit in the forthcoming year.

Conclusion:

On an overall basis, it can be said that the bank has performed well during the period under review. However, it can be inferred from this study that the bank can go long way in rendering better service to its members and can improve profitability by implementing the suggestions given. The bank has to ensure greater transparency in their overall working to rebuild the confidence of their business among its members.

References:

1. Amit Basak (2009), Appraisal of Urban Co-operative Banks: A Case Study, The IUP Journal of Accounting Research and Audit Practices, Vol. 8, Issue 1.
2. Bhagabata Behera (2014), Analysis of Financial Performance of Urban Cooperative Banks: A Case Study, Zenith International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research, Vol.4 (12), December.
3. Gupta, S.C., Fundamentals of Statistics, 6th revised and enlarged edition, Himalaya Publishing House, New Delhi.
4. Hajela, T.N., Co-operation, Principles, Problems and Practice, Konark Publishers Pvt., Ltd., New Delhi, 2000.
5. Kothari, C.R., "Research Methodology & Techniques". New Age International (P) Ltd, 2nd Edition.
6. www.tamilnadugramabank.com.